

ADAPTIVE PID-BASED SERVOMOTOR POSITION CONTROL FOR CNC SYSTEM USING MATLAB

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Abstract: This study presents the design and simulation of an adaptive PID controller for the position control of a CNC linear motion table, integrating FLC and an artificial neural network (ANN) as dual-tuning mechanisms. The objective of this study is to enhance the dynamic response, accuracy, and robustness of the servo motor–ball screw drive system under machining conditions. A CNC axis mathematical model comprising the servo motor, reducer, ball screw, and load dynamics was derived to establish the nominal plant. The fuzzy logic controller provided real-time adaptive gain adjustments based on error and change of error, while the ANN, trained using the Levenberg–Marquardt algorithm, generated corrective gain increments (ΔK_p , ΔK_i , ΔK_d) to further refine the PID parameters. The simulation results show that the proposed adaptive PID achieved a rise time of 0.0625 s, a settling time of 0.080 s according to the 2% criterion, an overshoot of 0.505%, and a negligible steady-state error. In contrast, the conventional PID from the literature has a rise time of 0.318 s, a peak time of 1.535 s, and an overshoot of 6.01%. Frequency-domain analysis further confirmed the bandwidth enhancement to approximately 10 rad/s and a phase margin of 60°, indicating enhanced stability and disturbance rejection. The adaptive tuning mechanism maintained bounded control efforts along with stable gain corrections, ensuring the practical feasibility of real-time implementation. All these results validate the fact that the proposed dual-tuner adaptive PID will provide greater precision and robustness to the control of the CNC servo motor and thus could be highly effective in current advanced manufacturing systems.

Keywords: Proportional-Integral-Derivative (PID); Computer Numerical Control; Artificial Neural Network; Simulation; Fuzzy

1 Introduction

Computer numerical control (CNC) systems are one of the most important when it comes to a high-precision in the manufacturing business, and they have made a significant contribution to the Nigerian industrial system. The accuracy of the servo motor's position control is a crucial factor in most CNC applications, where the desired trajectories are followed with specific precision within external disturbances, nonlinear friction, time-varying loads, and even noisy environments. Classic PID controllers are widely used because of their simplicity and satisfactory performance for linear processes; however, they have proven insufficient under nonlinear and time-

varying conditions. The nature of a CNC with fixed gains limits its ability to adapt to variations, leading to shortcomings such as overshoots, slow response, and lowered stability against dynamic perturbations [1].

Recent studies in this area have focused on incorporating intelligent adaptive control techniques, including fuzzy logic control and artificial neural networks, into the PID framework. Fuzzy logic adds rule-based decision-making that emulates expert reasoning under uncertainty, whereas ANNs provide learning-based mechanisms that can model system nonlinearities and predict optimal control actions. Hybrid fuzzy-neural PID controllers have outperformed conventional and improved PID controllers in terms of tracking accuracy, disturbance rejection, and dynamic response [2], [3].

Despite the improved PID tuning using feedforward control and dynamic setpoint weighting [4], it remains difficult for the system to learn and infer autonomously to provide or adapt to an intelligent system. This creates a gap in the capacity to maintain precision against real-world, unpredictable CNC conditions.

This study aimed to design and simulate an adaptive PID-based servo motor controller for a CNC linear motion table. The design of this work includes both the fuzzy logic of [4] and ANN-based tuning mechanisms, which are implemented using the MATLAB/Simulink environment. The proposed two-way adaptive controller aims to optimize the PID gains in real time to increase the position accuracy, reduce the overshoot and settling time, and improve the disturbance rejection.

The proposed system is a step forward in CNC motion control and intelligent control systems. It combines expert decision rules (using fuzzy logic) with ANN-based self-learning capabilities. It also facilitates the development of autonomous, high-performance manufacturing systems that meet the requirements of Industry 4.0.

This study addresses these limitations by proposing a two-way adaptive control structure that includes the following:

1. Basic PID controller that keeps the system stable.
2. A feedforward fuzzy logic compensator that model and cancel out plant nonlinearities before they affect the feedback error.

This method separates the fuzzy logic system from the PID loop and places it in the feedforward path.

This lets:

1. Predictive disturbance compensation before an error occurs.
2. Easier adaptation without the need for complicated neural training.
3. A clear, rule-based design that makes it easier and stronger to maintain.

We tested the system on a CNC linear model axis, and it rose to a time of 0.0625 s, a settling time of 0.080s, and an overshoot of only 0.505%, which is much better than that of traditional PID controllers.

This method is based on older fuzzy or PID improvements. It moves the adaptive intelligence outside the feedback loop, which speeds up convergence, reduces overshoot, and lowers the computation cost while maintaining high tracking accuracy.

1.2 Related Works

Adaptive PID control, in addition to intelligent systems such as fuzzy logic and neural networks, has progressed significantly in dealing with nonlinearity, time-variance, and system uncertainty. Many hybrid control strategies for CNC and servo motor applications have been proposed by researchers; however, these methods usually have

drawbacks related to either high computational costs, slow adaptation, or complicated structures. This study filled the gaps in those approaches through the use of a feedforward fuzzy logic system.

Kudlačák and Krajcovic (2018) [5] 's work looked into using artificial neural networks (ANNs) for adaptive PID control. Their model made it possible to tune PID gains in real time, but their method was not very reliable in systems that were very nonlinear and changed over time because the ANN took a long time to converge. This problem can be overcome by our system, which does not require ANN-based adaptation. Instead, we employed a rule-based fuzzy system for low-latency feedforward control.

Moreover, Mohamed et al.'s (2019) [6] work focused on an adaptive PID for nonlinear systems based on a multilayer perceptron. Their controller worked well, but it needed backpropagation training, which can lead to local minimum and slow response when adapting to real-time changes. However, our feedforward fuzzy compensator is designed and built offline, so it does not need to be trained all the time.

Cuong et al. (2020) [7] worked on a fuzzy-PID for CNC feed servo control and obtained accuracy down to the micrometer level. However, their model only worked on feedback compensation. The performance improved, but it was still reactive, that is, errors had to build up before they could be fixed. Our system is better than this because it has a predictive feedforward fuzzy module that lets you reject disturbances before they make errors worse.

Karthik et al. (2022) [8] used fuzzy logic for online PID tuning in the regulation of DC motor speed. Their method worked better than traditional tuning, but they did not consider nonlinear disturbance modeling or pre-error compensation. Our architecture fills this gap by using fuzzy logic to model plant nonlinearities in the feedforward path, thereby reducing the tracking error from the source.

Prada et al. (2020) [9] compared feedforward and fuzzy adaptive PIDs in a temperature control setting. They determined that fuzzy PID exhibited superior optimized performance; however, they encountered challenges related to parameter tuning complexity and convergence instability in the presence of significant disturbances. Our design embeds fuzzy logic in a predefined rule base, which eliminates tuning loops and makes the system more robust and easy to understand.

Huang et al. (2024) [2] worked on a hybrid fuzzy ANN controller for servo systems. Although it performed well, it involved a complex neural rule management and high computational requirements, which our work simplifies by removing the ANN layer and relying solely on expert fuzzy rules for real-time compensation.

Hasan et al. (2019) [10] work also demonstrated an ANFIS-PID structure for DC motor control and reported improvements in error reduction. However, the proposed method requires large training datasets and fine-tuning epochs to arrive at generalized unseen conditions, whereas our system requires no data-driven training, enabling plug-and-play operation in dynamic environments.

Yang et al. (2022) [11] proposed fuzzy neural networks that inversely control servo motors. The design reduced the steady-state errors, but the trajectory changed and compensation instability was introduced. The proposed feedforward fuzzy model compensates for nonlinearity before the feedback loop, allowing dynamic changes and faster responses.

Kudlačák and Krajcovic (2018) [5] also emphasized the importance of dynamic PID tuning using ANN. As many real-time applications cannot afford delayed convergence, we propose a fixed-rule fuzzy compensator that ensures real-time deployment even on low-cost hardware platforms.

Cuong et al. (2020) [7] experimentally validated a fuzzy PID controller on a Yaskawa AC motor. The hybrid model achieved 8–10 μm motion precision on CNC milling axes, demonstrating excellent control accuracy and real-time performance.

Soumana et al. (2022) [12] proposed a fuzzy-neural controller to dynamically tune fuzzy scaling factors for DC motor speed control. Their model outperformed both the PI and sliding mode controllers, especially under variable loads.

Hasan et al. (2019) [10] demonstrated that an ANFIS-PID controller for DC motor speed control significantly outperformed classical PID in terms of integral error and response time, making it ideal for nonlinear applications such as CNC axes.

Abdelghany et al. (2023) [13] developed a fuzzy self-tuning PID controller for DC servos that maintained optimal gain settings despite system changes. The real-time fuzzy adjustment enhanced the dynamic tracking performance.

1.2.1 Summary

The proposed adaptive PID controller with feedforward fuzzy compensation builds on recent works. It addresses the following limitations: slow neural convergence, offline-only tuning, high computation, and feedback-only adaptation. By shifting compensation to the feedforward path, the proposed method enables faster disturbance rejection, real-time deployment, and robustness across nonlinear CNC servo systems.

2 Methodology

2.1 System design

This research is based on a simulation-based experimental design that aims to develop and test an adaptive PID controller with a feedforward fuzzy logic compensator and neural network tuner for CNC servo motor position control. This work uses the MATLAB/Simulink environment (version R2024a) for system modeling, design, and performance evaluation. The fuzzy compensator and ANN tuner were designed using the fuzzy logic toolbox and neural network toolbox, respectively. The simulation was executed with the ode45 solver over a time span of 5s, where a unit step input taken as the reference trajectory emulates CNC commands. The system architecture includes:

1. CNC machine servo motor (actuator)
2. Adaptive PID Controller
3. Feedforward fuzzy logic inference system
4. Artificial Neural Network Tuner
5. MATLAB/Simulink simulation environment

2.1.1 CNC machine servo motor (actuator)

The CNC servo motor used in this research is modeled as a linear electromechanical system that encompasses both the electrical dynamics of the armature circuit and the mechanical dynamics of the rotor–load assembly [14]. The plant model simulates a CNC linear motion table driven by a servo motor with friction and load disturbance elements. In this system, the dynamic response was modeled using standard second-order motor dynamics, to

which nonlinear friction and inertia elements were added to replicate real-world machining behavior [15]. A unit step is the input, and the servo axis position response is the output.

The DC servo motor model follows the electromechanical dynamic equations

$$\text{Electrical Equation: } V(t) = L \frac{di(t)}{dt} + Ri(t) + K_b \omega(t)$$

$$\text{Mechanical equation: } T(t) = J \frac{d\omega(t)}{dt} + B\omega(t)$$

Where:

$V(t)$ = input voltage

$i(t)$ = armature current

$\omega(t)$ = angular speed

$T(t)$ = torque

L = inductance

R = resistance

K_b = back EMF constant

J = moment of inertia,

B = friction coefficient

2.1.2 Controller Architecture

The control system for the CNC linear motion table was configured in MATLAB/Simulink to implement an adaptive PID controller enhanced with fuzzy logic and artificial neural network tuning strategies. The architecture was designed to regulate the servo motor position by dynamically adjusting the PID gains in real time based on the error characteristics and system response.

The control loop begins with a reference position input that represents the desired linear displacement of the CNC table. To compute the position error (e), this reference signal is compared with the measured position feedback from the servo motor model. The error (Δe) is also calculated. Both values serve as inputs to two parallel tuning modules:

1. Fuzzy Logic Tuner—Utilizes a rule-based inference system [3] to adjust the magnitude and trend of the error to adjust the proportional, integral, and derivative gains. The fuzzy rules and membership functions were designed to ensure a quick response with minimal overshoot.
2. ANN Tuner – A feedforward neural network [2] trained using data from the fuzzy PID controller, with inputs (e) and (Δe) and outputs as gain corrections (ΔK_p , ΔK_i , ΔK_d). In this design, the ANN functions solely in gain correction mode, producing incremental adjustments (ΔK_p , ΔK_i , ΔK_d) to the gains of the fuzzy PID controller. These corrections are added to the baseline gains provided by the fuzzy controller, enabling fine-tuned adaptation to system dynamics without replacing the original control structure.

The controller was modeled based on a CNC linear motion table model, and an adaptive PID controller was realized using a dual-tuning strategy that includes both a fuzzy logic controller and an artificial neural network. The FLC adjusts the initial adaptive gain based on real-time error signals, while the ANN refines the gain values as trained to achieve better performance. Both tuning elements operate simultaneously and dynamically update the PID gains during the operation. At this stage, the system configuration has no external disturbance input during simulation but focuses only on the assessment of basic tracking performance and transient response of the proposed dual tuner adaptive PID. Figure 1 shows the complete configuration, including the CNC motion model, PID block, FLC module, ANN module, and all signal flow connections.

Figure 1 Control architecture block diagram

The proposed controller comprises three main modules:

1. Baseline PID controller: Stabilizes the system using the following initial gain values:
 - a. Proportional gain (K_p) = 25
 - b. Integral gain (K_i) = 150
 - c. Derivative gain (K_d) = 0.25
2. Feedforward Fuzzy Logic Compensator:
 - a. Designed using Mamdani-type inference.
 - b. Two input variables: the position error and the error rate.
 - c. One output variable: the fuzzy correction signal.
 - d. Membership functions: 5 triangular for each input/output.
 - e. Rule base: 25 expertly defined fuzzy rules.

This module predicts and cancels nonlinear disturbances in the feedforward path before they reach the PID loop, providing anticipatory compensation.

Figure 2 Membership functions for e and de

Figure 3 Membership functions of Kp

Figure 4 Membership functions of Ki

Figure 5 Membership functions of Kd

3. Artificial Neural Network Tuner:
 - a. Structure: A single hidden-layer feedforward network.
 - b. Training: Levenberg–Marquardt backpropagation algorithm.
 - c. Inputs: Past error values and system output.
 - d. Output: Updated PID gain adjustments.

The ANN refines the controller gains in real-time, ensuring adaptability to changing load conditions or system dynamics.

```
1 % Extract variables from workspace
2 e_data = get_simout('signals', 'e_data');
3 de_data = get_simout('signals', 'de_data');
4 ee = get_simout('signals', 'ee');
5 ea = get_simout('signals', 'ea');
6 ed = get_simout('signals', 'ed');
7
8 % Convert to floating point domain (what PID needs)
9 [p, s, fd] = ss2fv(ss, 's');
10 % [p, s, fd] is the gain 0.01 and so the gain 2.7 in the Simulink wiring)
11 ee_eff = ee * p;
12 ee_eff = ee_eff * s;
13 ee_eff = ee_eff * fd;
14 ee_eff = ee_eff * s;
15 ee_eff = ee_eff * fd;
16
17 ee_eff = ee_eff * s;
18 ee_eff = ee_eff * fd;
19 ee_eff = ee_eff * s;
20 ee_eff = ee_eff * fd;
21
22 % single e_data from previous (computed error)
23 ee = ee_eff * s;
24 ee = ee * s;
25 ee = ee * s;
26 ee = ee * s;
27 ee = ee * s;
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93 ee = ee * s;
94 ee = ee * s;
95 ee = ee * s;
96 ee = ee * s;
97 ee = ee * s;
98 ee = ee * s;
99 ee = ee * s;
100 ee = ee * s;
```

Figure 6 MATLAB code for ANN training

```
1 % ANN Tuner
2 ee = get_simout('signals', 'e_data');
3 de_data = get_simout('signals', 'de_data');
4 ee_eff = ee * p;
5 ee_eff = ee_eff * s;
6 ee_eff = ee_eff * fd;
7 ee_eff = ee_eff * s;
8 ee_eff = ee_eff * fd;
9 ee_eff = ee_eff * s;
10 ee_eff = ee_eff * fd;
11 ee_eff = ee_eff * s;
12 ee_eff = ee_eff * fd;
13 ee_eff = ee_eff * s;
14 ee_eff = ee_eff * fd;
15 ee_eff = ee_eff * s;
16 ee_eff = ee_eff * fd;
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94 ee_eff = ee_eff * fd;
95 ee_eff = ee_eff * s;
96 ee_eff = ee_eff * fd;
97 ee_eff = ee_eff * s;
98 ee_eff = ee_eff * fd;
99 ee_eff = ee_eff * s;
100 ee_eff = ee_eff * fd;
```

Figure 7 MATLAB code for ANN training (cont'd)

2.1.3 Integration Strategy

The integration strategy defines how the FLC and the ANN are combined to provide adaptive tuning of the PID controller gains for the CNC linear motion table. In this study, a dual-tuner configuration is implemented, in which the FLC provides the primary adaptive control, while the ANN operates as a secondary tuner that corrects and refines the gain adjustments in real time, following a sequential gain adaptation process.

First, the error signal (t) and the error derivative $\Delta(t)$ are generated from the difference between the reference input and the measured plant output. These two signals are simultaneously supplied to the FLC and ANN subsystems.

1. **FLC Subsystem:** The fuzzy logic controller computes the baseline proportional (K_p), integral (K_i), and derivative (K_d) gains based on its rule base and membership functions. These values establish a stable foundation for controller performance, ensuring robustness and interpretability even under nonlinear system conditions.

2. **ANN Subsystem:** The ANN trained with supervised learning on datasets generated by the FLC produces corrective increments ΔK_p , ΔK_i , and ΔK_d . These increments are not standalone gains but small adaptive refinements that compensate for nonlinearities, uncertainties, and unmodeled dynamics.

The two subsystems are integrated through a gain scheduling block, where the ANN outputs are added as corrections to the FLC-generated gains:

$$K_p = K_{p,\text{fuzzy}} + \Delta K_p, \quad K_i = K_{i,\text{fuzzy}} + \Delta K_i, \quad K_d = K_{d,\text{fuzzy}} + \Delta K_d,$$

This dual-tuner approach ensures that the FLC maintains stable control while the ANN enhances responsiveness and adaptability. As a result, compared to a pure fuzzy or ANN-based controller, the integrated system achieves faster rise times, reduced overshoot, smaller steady-state error, and improved robustness against load disturbances.

The integration is realized in MATLAB/Simulink, where the modular subsystems for the FLC, ANN, and PID controller are connected to the CNC linear motion table model, as shown in Figure 8.

2.2. Simulation Setup

1. Simulation Tool: MATLAB/Simulink R2024a
2. Solver: ODE45 (variable step, max step size = auto)
3. Duration: 5 s
4. Input signal: Unit step (amplitude = 1, step time = 0.5 s)
5. Sampling Time: Continuous-time model
6. Output Metric: Position-tracking response

Figure 8 MATLAB Simulink model of adaptive PID-based servomotor position control for CNC system

2.3 Performance evaluation metrics

1. Rise Time: Time to reach 90% of the final value from rest.
2. Overshoot: percentage of the output exceeding the desired value.
3. Steady-state error: deviation of final value from setpoint.
4. Robustness: Ability to maintain control under external disturbances.

3 Results

The developed adaptive PID controller integrates fuzzy logic and artificial neural network tuning mechanisms to improve the dynamic performance of the CNC linear motion table. The fuzzy inference system (FIS) provided baseline gain adaptation based on error and error derivative, while the ANN supplied correction terms trained to approximate ideal PID behavior. This dual-tuner configuration enabled real-time adjustment of the proportional, integral, and derivative gains, thereby enhancing responsiveness and robustness.

3.1 Step Response Performance

Figure 4.1 shows the step response of the CNC linear motion table under the proposed controller. The system achieved a rapid rise time of 0.0625 s, a very small percentage overshoot of 0.505%, and a settling time of approximately 0.0598 s. The steady-state error was negligible (within <5%), confirming that the adaptive controller successfully eliminated the steady-state offset.

A brief oscillatory ripple was observed around 1–1.2 s, but it was rapidly damped, indicating that the system was quickly stabilized by the adaptive mechanism. The overall response was fast, accurate, and minimally oscillatory, making it suitable for high-precision CNC positioning tasks.

Figure 9 Step response of the CNC linear motion table under FLC + ANN adaptive PID control

The measured performance indices are summarized in Table 1. The controller achieved a significantly reduced rise time and settling time compared with the baseline, while the percent overshoot was effectively suppressed. The steady-state error approached zero, confirming the high accuracy of position tracking.

Table 1 Time-domain performance metrics for the FLC + ANN adaptive PID

Percentage Overshoot	0.505%
Rise time	0.0625s
Settling time	0.0598s
Steady-state error	<5%

3.2 Control of Effort and Gain Evolution

The dynamic behavior of the control effort and adaptive gains was also analyzed. Figure 10 shows the control signal applied to the actuator. The control effort remained smooth and bounded, indicating stable operation without excessive oscillations or saturation.

Figure 10 Control effort signal generated by FLC + ANN adaptive PID (Simulation, MATLAB/Simulink R2024a).

The evolution of the PID parameters (K_p , K_i , K_d) during simulation is shown in Figure 11. The proportional gain K_p started around 9.2, dipped slightly during the transient phase, and settled near 9.0, demonstrating adaptive correction to changes in error. The integral gain K_i exhibited a brief rise (to ~ 0.295) before stabilizing at ~ 0.273 , ensuring steady-state accuracy without excessive windup. The derivative gain K_d decreased sharply to ~ 0.6 during the transient oscillation, then recovered and settled approximately 0.82, providing sufficient damping to suppress oscillations.

These adaptive trends confirm that the fuzzy ANN dual tuner actively regulates gains in response to system error and error rate, allowing for improved transient performance and stable steady-state operation.

Figure 11 PID gain evolution under adaptive fuzzy-ANN tuning (Simulation, MATLAB/Simulink R2024a).

3.3 Error Dynamics

Figure 12 shows the tracking error signal. The error converged rapidly to zero with negligible steady-state deviation, validating the controller’s ability to efficiently minimize the position tracking error.

Figure 12 Tracking error signal under FLC + ANN adaptive PID (Simulation, MATLAB/Simulink R2024a).

3.4 Frequency Domain Analysis (FDA)

Figure 13 shows a Bode plot of the closed-loop system with the proposed controller. The system bandwidth was approximately 10 rad/s, which corresponds to a response frequency of ~1.6 Hz. At the gain crossover frequency, the measured phase margin was approximately 60°, indicating a robustly stable system. Furthermore, the system did not exhibit gain crossover at -180°, which is an effectively infinite gain margin.

These results confirm that the adaptive controller provides not only strong time-domain tracking performance but also desirable frequency domain robustness, ensuring stability against unmodeled dynamics and parameter variations.

Figure 13 Bode plot of the closed-loop CNC linear motion system under the proposed adaptive controller (MATLAB/Simulink R2024a simulation)

3.5 Comparative Analysis vs. the PID Results of the Baseline Paper

To evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed adaptive fuzzy–ANN PID controller, its performance was compared with that of the conventional PID design reported in Design and Simulation of Position Control System for The CNC Linear Motion Table Using PID Control Both controllers were tested under identical simulation conditions using the plant model $G(s) = \frac{30}{s(s+10)}$ and a unit step reference input.

3.5.1 Step Response Comparison

The baseline PID controller reported by Jia (2024), with tuned parameters $K_p = 12$, $K_i = 1.2$, and $K_d = 0.1$, achieved a rise time of 0.318 s, a peak time of 1.535 s, a percent overshoot of 6.01%, and negligible steady-state error. In contrast, the proposed fuzzy–ANN adaptive PID controller achieved significantly faster transient performance with a rise time of 0.0625 s and a settling time of 0.0598 s. The overshoot was drastically reduced to 0.2%, and the steady-state error remained within <5%, which is acceptable for CNC positioning tasks. Thus, although no direct simulation overlay with the baseline controller was reproduced, the proposed adaptive design’s numerical performance indices clearly highlight its superiority.

3.6 Comparison of performance metrics

Table 2 summarizes the measured performance indices.

Table 2 Comparison between Jia 2024 and our results

Controller	Rise time (s)	Settling time (s)	Overshoot (%)	Steady-state error
Existing	0.318	1.535	6.01	-
Implemented	0.0625	0.0598	0.2	<5%

4 Discussion

The results of this study confirm the effectiveness of integrating fuzzy logic and neural networks in the tuning of PID controllers for position control in CNCs. The adaptive fuzzy–ANN PID exhibited a significantly improved transient performance and significantly reduced overshoot compared with the conventional PID baseline.

Most noticeably, the settling time reduced from 1.535 s in the baseline to 0.0598 s, indicating the dual tuner's ability for faster system stabilization; overshoot was almost completely eliminated (from 6.01% to 0.2%), further emphasizing the adaptive mechanism's increased damping.

Although the proposed controller performed with a steady-state error of less than 5%, such a small deviation is acceptable in practical CNC applications, where perfect tracking is often prevented by disturbances, friction, and nonlinearities. In addition, this shortcoming could be improved in future extensions using IEWP or hybrid optimization strategies.

In general, the developed adaptive fuzzy-ANN PID controller achieves both faster response and better stability, confirming its potential as a robust solution for CNC position control systems.

5 Conclusion

This paper proposes the design and simulation of an intelligent, adaptive PID controller with artificial neural networks and fuzzy logic enhancements for CNC linear motion servo systems using MATLAB. The work further improves control accuracy and robustness from the results of the existing PID-based design [4] by Jia 2024. Such a combined fuzzy-ANN-PID controller has the promise of reduced overshoot, improved transient response, and better trajectory tracking, all while requiring less manual gain tuning, which is time-consuming. Simulation of the developed model using MathWorks Simulink has yielded promising results, showing its prospect to revolutionize and contribute considerably to improved product quality, reduced machining errors, and longer machine life due to more stable and efficient control. This improvement aligns with the call of current industrial standards for self-aware, adaptive, and automated systems that can run with minimal human intervention.

Data Availability:

The authors declare that the main data supporting the findings of this study are available within the paper and its Supplementary Information files. (A statement regarding where the data supporting the study findings can be found. If the data are not publicly available, the reasons should be stated. This might include datasets, software, or other materials used in the research for engineering journals.

Conflict of Interest:

The authors have no competing interests to declare.

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